

Reference Management Software: Comparative Analysis of RefWorks and Zotero

Authors : Sujit K. Basak

Abstract : This paper presents a comparison of reference management software between RefWorks and Zotero. The results were drawn by comparing two software and the novelty of this paper is the comparative analysis of software and it has shown that RefWorks can import more information from the Google Scholar for the researchers. This finding could help to know researchers to use the reference management software.

Keywords : analysis, comparative analysis, reference management software, researchers

Conference Title : ICSET 2014 : International Conference on Society, Education and Technology

Conference Location : Cape Town, South Africa

Conference Dates : November 06-07, 2014